

Advances in the field of RNA 3D structure prediction and modeling, with purely theoretical approaches, and with the use of experimental data

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Abstract

Recent advancements in RNA three-dimensional (3D) structure prediction and modeling have provided significant insights into RNA biology, highlighting the essential role of RNA in cellular functions and its potential in therapeutic applications. This review summarizes the latest developments in computational methods, focusing on the incorporation of artificial intelligence and machine learning, which have markedly improved the precision and efficiency of RNA structure predictions. Attention is given to the integration of new experimental data types, including advanced cryo-EM techniques and improvements in high-throughput sequencing, which have transformed RNA structure modeling. The combination of these experimental advances with sophisticated computational methods, especially deep learning, represents a significant leap forward in RNA structure determination. We highlight the outcomes of community-wide prediction challenges RNA-Puzzles and CASP, which assess the current state and limitations of existing methods, guiding future research directions. Future perspectives are discussed, focusing on the impact of RNA 3D structure prediction in understanding RNA mechanisms and its implications for drug discovery and RNA-targeted therapies, opening new avenues in molecular biology.

1. Introduction

Ribonucleic acids (RNAs) function in core cellular processes including gene regulation, RNA splicing, and protein synthesis. Elucidating these processes requires knowledge of RNA structures and their interactions with various molecular partners. The experimental determination of RNA structures at high-resolution, which allows the determination of individual atomic features as well as atomic interactions, is difficult, and in many cases not possible. Unlike proteins, RNA's flexibility and inherent dynamics make techniques like RNA crystallography challenging. As a result, complete high-resolution structures are available for an extremely small fraction of all the known RNA molecules that are important for numerous

fundamental cellular processes. As of 5th July 2024, 1900 RNA-only structures and 7836 RNA complexes with other macro-molecules were available in the Protein Data Bank (PDB)^{1,2}, including 1192/3890 solved by X-ray crystallography, 590/764 by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, 116/3173 by cryo-electron microscopy, and 2/9 by other methods. The largest RNA sequences, for which three-dimensional (3D) structures were determined, were large ribosomal RNAs (complexed with proteins in large ribosomal subunits or entire ribosomes), typically approximately ~3500 ribonucleotide nucleotides (nts) and viral RNAs, e.g., bacteriophage MS2 genome³ (PDB id: 5TC1). On the other hand, the current edition of the RNACentral database^{4,5} of non-coding RNA molecules archives ~35 million RNA sequences as of RNACentral release 24, with the longest RNAs reaching hundreds of thousands of nucleotides.

This review focuses on the most recently developed methods for modeling the 3D structure of RNA molecules and on the computational methods used for RNA 3D structure determination using experimental data. We recognize the critical importance of predicting RNA secondary structures, but we omit these methods from this article due to space limitations. We exclude historical details, and refrain from reviewing the majority of RNA 3D structure modeling or structure determination algorithms and methods developed over the years, which have been extensively reviewed previously⁶⁻⁹. We start by reviewing a few methods that performed best in the context of the recent community-wide prediction challenges, followed by the discussion of the newest approaches that have not yet been thoroughly tested by the research community, but offer inspiration for new developments. Our goal is to provide a strategic overview of methodological approaches for building RNA 3D models with or without the use of experimental data, illustrated with the best-performing and newest methods, rather than to provide a comprehensive catalog of all computational methods that exist in the field of computational structural biology of RNA.

2. Community-wide prediction challenges:

Community-wide prediction challenges play a crucial role in evaluating and advancing the field of computational RNA structure prediction. In case of RNA 3D structure, the blind prediction challenge RNA-Puzzles¹⁰⁻¹³ has been going on for more than a decade. The Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction (CASP) is a community-wide experiment that evaluates primarily the performance of protein structure prediction methods. In the most recent experiment CASP15, RNA 3D structure prediction has been included as a separate category¹⁴⁻¹⁸. These two blind prediction challenges serve as valuable benchmarks, fostering healthy competition, mutual inspiration between RNA 3D structure predictors, and pushing the boundaries of the state-of-the-art. The results from these challenges offer key insights into what is currently achievable and the limitations that remain. At the time of the writing of this article, CASP16 has started, and will provide an update of the state-of-the art in the field in publications that are expected to appear by the end of 2025.

Research groups that performed best in RNA-Puzzles and CASP, typically applied a combination of a diverse array of computational methods. It is worth emphasizing that the best RNA 3D structure prediction methods (at least according to the last evaluations) are rooted in approaches that were successful in the last 20 years. Template-based and fragment assembly methods such as ModeRNA¹⁹, RNAComposer²⁰ or Vfold3D²¹ were commonly used, and predictions obtained with such approaches showed high levels of accuracy in cases where 3D structures of clearly related RNA molecules were already available. For the cases of de novo 3D structure prediction, most of the best-performing groups used hierarchical and hybrid approaches that often involved splitting the larger RNA molecules into smaller modules that could be modeled individually (with or without templates). The global architectures of RNA molecules were then

typically assembled with methods for sampling the conformation space with Monte Carlo methods, coupled with various potentials and scoring functions. Simulation methods that were frequently involved in successful hybrid RNA 3D structure predictions include ROSETTA-FARNA/FAR-FAR^{22,23}, IsRNA²⁴, RNAJP²⁵, SimRNA^{26,27}, and BRiQ²⁸. It is important to emphasize that all successful predictors used additional constraints and restraints to guide the simulations of RNA 3D structure formation. All groups used additional information about secondary structure, predicted computationally or from the literature, whenever available, as well as various other types of information derived from manually-verified sources. Whenever time permitted, the modelers optimized the geometry of the final models to be submitted for evaluation with additional fine-grained methods, often based on physics-based energy functions.

The series of RNA-Puzzles and the most recent RNA structure prediction evaluation in CASP have clearly revealed the capabilities of current methods and their limitations. Firstly, no single fully automated method has been found so far to accurately predict RNA 3D structures for all types of RNA molecules. Successful predictions almost always include a combination of various tools. Secondly, the approaches that were most successful to date, involve (at least on some level) the combination of coarse-grained modeling with a Monte Carlo approach, with scoring by a knowledge-based statistical potential. On the other hand, purely physics-based simulations have not yet produced structural predictions of comparably high accuracy. The deep learning (DL) approaches performed quite well according to CASP15 evaluation, but, at that time, they still remained inferior to the most successful hybrid modeling approaches. Thirdly, successful predictions usually utilized additional information from literature and database searches, particularly various types of experimental data.

In general, the most successful RNA 3D structure modeling groups in RNA-Puzzles and CASP15 could predict the overall architectures of most RNA molecules with reasonable accuracy, while some structures presented considerable challenges. The most difficult targets were artificial nano-structures. The RNA secondary structures and the canonical base pairs were usually predicted correctly. However, accurate prediction of structural details including non-canonical pairs, loop conformations, long-range interactions, and the interactions of RNA molecules with other molecules often remain elusive. As of today, the accurate prediction of RNA 3D structure remains challenging if no 3D structures of related molecules are available, which could serve as modeling templates.

3. Recent advances in computational methods for RNA 3D structure prediction:

3.1. RNA 3D Structure model building

Two best-performing groups according to the CASP15 evaluation²⁹ used new approaches. The top-performing group AIchemy_RNA2 used the recently developed BRiQ potential³⁰. This knowledge-based energy function was designed to comprehensively account for the complex orientation-dependent interactions observed between nucleobases, as well as between nucleobases and the oxygen atoms in the RNA backbone. 3D orientational analysis, the BRiQ model extended this to a six-dimensional (6D) orientational space. The interactions involving bases and oxygen atoms in backbones are strongly orientation-dependent, and they are much better captured in the six-dimensional interaction space. The densities in the 6D space were derived from known RNA 3D structures using kernel density estimations, rather than histogram statistics used in many other methods. This allowed obtaining a smoother energy landscape, with the local minima corresponding to the preferred interactions observed in experimentally determined structures. Additionally, the method introduced a corrective measure to diminish the influence

of indirect base-base interactions by scaling statistical energy scores with quantum mechanical calculations, thereby enhancing the model's ability to accurately represent both local and global interactions.

Among the methods used by the runner-up in CASP15 (Chen group) the RNAJP (RNA Junction Prediction) method was developed recently^{9,25}, which puts particular emphasis on accurate modeling of RNA structures with junction. At its core, RNAJP uses a coarse-grained model that represents RNA molecules at both nucleotide and helix levels. This dual-level simplification facilitates efficient sampling in 3D space, making the model particularly effective for junction structures. In addition, RNAJP incorporates known recurrent 3D motif information to model hairpin and internal loops and considers explicitly non-canonical base pairing and base stacking interactions as well as long-range loop-loop interactions. Overall, this approach enables RNAJP to capture the complex, multi-branched nature of RNA junctions more accurately than earlier methods.

Both RNA-BRiQ and RNAJP address the critical issue in RNA 3D structure modeling, namely the correct modeling of non-canonical base-pairs as well as stacking interactions, which are particularly relevant for the correct modeling of helix junction topologies and long-range interactions between the loops. Compared to the prediction of canonical pairs, these interactions were thus far extremely difficult to predict from RNA sequence, and were rarely used to guide RNA folding simulations. It will be interesting to see if these innovative solutions are successfully implemented in other methods, leading to further improvement of the RNA 3D structure prediction accuracy.

Two independent assessments in CASP15 ranked two groups tied for third place¹⁴: RNAPolis (Szachniuk group)¹⁶ and GeneSilico (our group)¹⁷. The Szachniuk group used computational workflows based on their previously developed method, RNAComposer²⁰. Our group employed our previously developed workflow involving ModeRNA¹⁹, SimRNA^{26,3132}. Despite relatively minor methodological updates to the previously published methods, both groups generated, on average, better predictions than any of the newly developed methods based on DL.

The Das group (consistently among the top-performers in RNA-Puzzles) has developed FARFAR2³³, an evolution of the original FARFAR (Fragment Assembly of RNA with Full-Atom Refinement) protocol. This new version incorporates updated RNA fragment libraries and helix modeling techniques. FARFAR2 has shown improved accuracy in reconstructing RNA structures in RNA-Puzzles trials, even without experimental data or expert intervention. This protocol represents a significant step forward in the prediction of complex RNA folds, providing a more robust toolset for RNA structure prediction³³. Interestingly, another group recently developed P-FARFAR2³⁴, an enhancement that increases FARFAR2's ability to sample low-energy structures via multithreaded exploration of random configurations in a greedy manner, contributing to improved RNA structure prediction capabilities. The Das group has also developed another improvement based on the Rosetta framework, a stepwise Monte Carlo (SWM) optimization method SWM, whose primary moves are the stepwise addition moves that allow building of small RNA 3D structures (e.g., for local 3D motifs) involving non-canonical pairs one nucleotide at a time, starting from conformations with helices only³⁵. This approach has been recently improved by another group, which introduced a more efficient sampling strategy in the method called SMCP³⁶.

The field of protein structure prediction has been revolutionized by DL approaches, particularly with the pioneering AlphaFold/AlphaFold2 methods^{37,38} and other related approaches such as RoseTTaFold³⁹ and OpenFold⁴⁰. However, these methods have not yet achieved the same level of success in predicting 3D structures for RNA molecules. Very recently, AlphaFold3 has been published⁴¹, showing some improvement in the 3D structure prediction for RNAs and RNA-protein complexes over competing methods, but the accuracy of these predictions is still significantly lower than that of proteins. We discuss the AlphaFold3 approach to RNA modeling in comparison to other methods later in this article.

As Schneider et al.⁴² discussed the possible reasons why AlphaFold-like methods haven't yet been achieved for RNA 3D structure prediction. In particular, compared to proteins, there is significantly less data on experimentally determined RNA structures, and there are fewer RNA sequence alignments, especially high-quality alignments with multiple diverse sequences. This limits the ability of DL models to learn the complex relationships between sequence and structure for RNA. Despite this, recent advancements in DL are pushing the boundaries of RNA structure prediction and it is likely that DL will eventually take the lead in RNA structure prediction as well.

Current deep learning methods for RNA 3D structure prediction primarily focus on determining a single, optimal structure for a given RNA sequence or just a few optimal alternative structures. In contrast, classical methods based on simulations provide a more comprehensive exploration of the RNA energy and structure landscape. The simulation-based methods allow for a detailed investigation of the RNA folding process, capturing the dynamic nature of RNA molecules and the various intermediate states they may adopt. Consequently, while deep learning methods offer rapid and often accurate predictions, simulation-based techniques continue to provide a richer understanding of RNA folding mechanisms and energetics (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Simulation-based and deep-learning-based methods for RNA structure prediction. DL methods typically aim to predict the final folded structure of RNA molecules. In contrast, simulation-based methods explore the folding pathways, offering insights into the formation of alternative structures and the conformational transitions between them. Given that RNA molecules exhibit shapeshifting behavior more prominently than typical protein molecules, this aspect needs to be considered accordingly in RNA 3D structure prediction.

Here we review the latest developments in DL approaches for RNA 3D structure prediction. Most of the preprints describing this work claim better performance than other methods, but it remains to be seen their head-to-head comparison in blind, objective benchmarks, so we refrain from commenting on their objective accuracy, but instead focus on the key methodology used.

Geometry-based deep learning methods are distinguished by their focus on modeling spatial relationships in RNA molecules. These approaches predict geometric features such as distances, angles, and orientations between atoms and nucleotides, which are critical for accurate 3D structure reconstruction. This methodology reflects a significant trend toward integrating complex geometric data directly into predictive models. Several core features are commonly shared among various approaches. These methods typically employ representations that capture the spatial configurations of RNA structures and convert atomic coordinates into relational geometric data such as distances and angles between atoms. Geometry-based DL methods focus on optimizing how each atom interacts with its local environment. By accurately predicting the local interactions, geometry-based models guide the assembly of global RNA 3D structures.

Examples of recently developed geometry-based DL methods aiming specifically for RNA 3D structure prediction include trRosettaRNA⁴³, DeepFoldRNA⁴⁴, PAMNet⁴⁵, and EpRNA⁴⁶. trRosettaRNA first employs a DL network, RNAformer, akin to AlphaFold2 Evoformer. It utilizes a transformer-based module to analyze a multiple sequence alignment (MSA) and a predicted secondary structure to capture how the MSA information influences the predicted geometric features between all possible pairs of nucleotides in the RNA molecule. The information is then passed to Rosetta software⁴⁷ to use these predicted features along with its own energy terms to refine and generate full-atom 3D models. DeepFoldRNA also predicts spatial restraints (distance maps and inter-residue orientations) from MSAs, using deep self-attention neural networks to convert them into negative log-likelihood potentials. RNA 3D structure models are generated using gradient-based folding simulations based on the minimization of the potential. PAMNet is a graph neural network (GNN). It represents RNA structures as multiplex graphs, where separate layers encode local and non-local atomic interactions. An attention-based DL module is employed to integrate the contributions of each interaction type for the final structure prediction using physics-based principles. EpRNA utilizes a Euclidean neural network, with a Euclidean distance matrix that captures the geometric relationships between all pairs of residues in the RNA 3D structure. The matrix is then used by a convolutional neural network (CNN) to predict the inter-residue distances, which are converted into 3D coordinates using discrete molecular dynamics (MD) simulation with constraints.

End-to-End (E2E) learning approaches in RNA 3D structure prediction are designed to directly translate RNA sequences into their final 3D structures, eliminating the need for intermediate stages such as secondary structure prediction or estimation of geometric parameters. In E2E approaches, the specification of concrete features for analysis and prediction is typically minimized or entirely handled internally by the model. This approach reduces the requirement for researchers to understand and define the specific biochemical or structural features of RNA molecules to be considered. Recent developments in E2E methods have seen the incorporation of large language models (LLMs), which are useful for capturing long-range dependencies within RNA sequence data.

Examples of recently developed geometry-based DL methods for RNA 3D structure prediction include RhoFold+ (previously named E2Efold-3D)⁴⁸ and ERNIE-RNA⁴⁹. RhoFold+ utilizes a transformer-based architecture, a common framework in natural language processing. In addition to 3D structure prediction, RhoFold+ incorporates RNA secondary structure predictions into its learning process. Like techniques

used in AlphaFold, RhoFold+ employs a self-distillation strategy where the model's own predictions are used to iteratively refine and improve its training process. The model is also optimized for computational efficiency, with a reported average inference time significantly lower than traditional methods. ERNIE-RNA employs a self-supervised training approach, differing from RhoFold+ by not using an extensive LLM. ERNIE-RNA is based on a masked language modeling technique where the model predicts masked nucleotides from the contextual sequence data. This method allows the model to learn the correlations between sequence and structure indirectly, avoiding the computational demands associated with large LLM architectures.

Foundation models (FMs) represent a broader concept within DL. They are pre-trained on massive datasets encompassing various features, which allows them to learn generalizable representations of the underlying data. Unlike E2E models, FMs are not specifically designed for a single task like RNA structure prediction. Instead, they serve as a foundation upon which more specialized models can be built. For RNA 3D structure prediction, an FM can be pre-trained on a vast dataset of RNA sequences, a smaller dataset of known secondary structures, and a relatively very small set of RNA 3D structures. This approach does not rely on data annotation, and allows the model to infer various characteristics of RNAs. A pre-trained model can then be fine-tuned for specific tasks, such as predicting base-pairs or interatomic distances. FMs can leverage the power of large datasets for pre-training, reducing the data demands for specialized tasks like RNA 3D structure prediction.

The RNA foundation model (RNA-FM)⁵⁰ utilized a self-supervised learning strategy from a set of 23 million RNA sequences sourced from the RNACentral database⁵. The training process of RNA-FM was divided into two distinct phases: a pre-training phase where general features of RNA sequences were learned in a task-agnostic manner, and a fine-tuning phase where the model was adapted to specific RNA-related tasks. This dual-phase learning strategy enabled RNA-FM to be adapted to various applications, including RNA structure prediction. UniRNA⁵¹ is an ensemble of foundation models ranging from 25 to 400 million parameters, pre-trained on a dataset of 1 billion RNA sequences for a spectrum of structural and functional downstream tasks. RiNALMo⁵² was trained on curated 36 million ncRNA sequences from the RNACentral database augmented by several other RNA databases, resulting in a 650 million parameter transformer encoder. ATOM-1⁵³ is a specialized foundation model for RNA secondary and 3D structure prediction trained on chemical mapping data. A foundation model is also used in RhoFold+⁵⁴ to model RNA sequence patterns and structural tendencies. This training enables RhoFold+ to mitigate the issue of data scarcity that hampers RNA structure prediction.

Hybrid deep learning approaches in RNA 3D structure prediction typically integrate elements of both end-to-end prediction and explicit geometric modeling, bridging the gap between DL techniques and more traditional methods. These approaches typically employ machine learning to generate initial predictions which are then refined using physics-based models to improve accuracy and biological relevance. The primary advantage of hybrid methods is their ability to leverage the strengths of computational predictions for initial structure approximation while utilizing well-established physical and chemical principles to ensure the final model's fidelity to real-world molecular structures. This methodological synthesis allows for the accurate modeling of RNA structures by balancing the speed and scalability of DL with the precision of empirical physics-based simulations.

Examples of hybrid approaches include DRfold⁵⁵, NuFold⁵⁶, and RoseTTAFoldNA⁴⁷. DRfold integrates end-to-end learning with deep geometric potentials. It begins with the embedding of sequence and

secondary structure predictions into transformer networks, to predict nucleotide rotation matrices and translation vectors. These predictions are used alongside geometric potentials to construct data for structure optimization. NuFold employs an iterative refinement process akin to AlphaFold's recycling mechanism, tailored for RNA. RoseTTAFoldNA employs a three-track neural network architecture adapted from the RoseTTAFold method developed for protein structure prediction⁴⁷. It extends protein 3D structure prediction to nucleic acids. It uses end-to-end DL to initially predict structural features and subsequently refines these predictions with physics-based modeling.

AlphaFold3⁴¹ is one of the most recent additions to the growing set of DL approaches for RNA 3D structure prediction. It combines E2E learning principles with specific novel architectures designed to enhance predictive accuracy and efficiency for a very broad range of biomolecular structures, including proteins, nucleic acids, and small molecules. Unlike AlphaFold2³⁸, which focused on specific geometry-related features in protein structures, it uses a diffusion-based architecture with a generative model to directly predict raw atom coordinates. The application of the diffusion model abstracts away some of the geometric complexity across different scales from local stereochemistry to larger molecular structures.

Deep learning for prediction of structural features other than RNA 3D structure or secondary structure.

Some of the recent DL methods do not predict explicitly the RNA 3D structure, but rather they generate predictions of structural features that can be used (e.g., by other methods, including non-DL methods) to generate 3D models. AutoRNA⁵⁷ is an example of a neural network based on a variational autoencoder, which takes as input an RNA sequence and predicts distances between the ribonucleotide residues. RNA-TorsionBERT⁵⁸ is a language model that predicts RNA torsional angles from sequence data.

Comparisons of the performance of new DL methods with non-DL methods were reported by a few independent recent studies. Nithin et al.⁵⁹ and Bernard et al.⁶⁰ have run DL and non-DL methods in an automated way on several datasets of RNA 3D structures. Both groups concluded that DL approaches do not solve the problem of RNA 3D structure prediction as of yet. They found that, on average, the DL models exhibit somewhat better accuracy in terms of metrics that assess global similarity to the experimentally determined structures, such as root mean square deviation (RMSD) of the atomic coordinates or its various derivatives. However, they are not significantly better and often worse than non-DL methods in terms of measures that assess details of intra-molecular interactions, particularly non-Watson-Crick base pairs and complex 3D motifs such as G-quadruplexes. These types of head-to-head comparisons have two weaknesses that give an advantage to DL methods. One is that many of the datasets used for testing contain RNA structures that could have been used for training the methods being compared, which is especially true for the most recently developed methods (including all DL methods). Another issue is that all the methods were run with default parameters and without special preparation of the input with additional data. Fully automated prediction based only on RNA sequence is the typical default mode of DL methods; for instance, they predict secondary structure and long-range contacts automatically. On the other hand, many non-DL methods are not expected to perform optimally with such minimalistic input, and they require additional restraints as well as adjustment of parameters, for instance, to increase the simulation time for longer sequences. This explains why new DL methods did not outperform the earlier non-DL approaches in the CASP15 benchmark¹⁴ in which many of the RNA prediction targets weren't very closely related to previously known RNA 3D structures, and in which the modelers could adjust the parameters of their methods case by case.

Nithin et al.⁵⁹ highlighted the complementary nature of the DL and non-DL approaches, suggesting a synergistic strategy that combines DL for global structural predictions (especially for long RNA sequences for which no closely related 3D structures are known) with non-DL methods for detailed modeling of molecular interactions. This approach utilizes the strengths of both methods and enables the correct use of restraints on secondary structure and other interactions, as well as the integration of diverse biochemical and biophysical data to enhance prediction accuracy. We have come to very similar conclusions independently and have used a similar strategy from the start of the CASP16 event (ongoing at the time of the writing of this article). Briefly, in one of our prediction workflows, we initially run several DL methods, compare the models generated, and in case of similarities, we extract restraints that are subsequently used to guide RNA 3D structure folding by SimRNA²⁷, in addition to other restraints typically used. From our experience with DL and non-DL methods so far, the current versions of DL methods (in particular AlphaFold3) exhibit a strong tendency to fold RNA into very compact structures, often more compact than the real structures, e.g., with terminal loops in the hairpin-loop structures forced to bind to each other or to make interactions with other helical regions. On the other hand, if such long-range interactions actually do exist in the RNA 3D structures, non-DL methods are worse than DL methods in predicting such interactions correctly, and they tend to form insufficiently compact structures, especially for long RNA sequences. This observation suggests an obvious potential for synergy between these two types of methods for future development.

3.2 RNA 3D structure model evaluation

In addition to methods that generate RNA 3D structure models, other approaches have been developed for computational assessment of RNA 3D structures, which aim at evaluating conformations generated by 3D structure modeling methods. These methods may be used for assessing how accurate one specific 3D model is, for discriminating native-like structures from a large pool of models with variable quality, or for relative ranking of alternative models for the same molecule. Many of the earliest methods developed for this purpose utilized statistical potentials. They quantify the similarity of values of structural parameters such as interatomic distances, bond angles, torsion angles, non-bonded interactions, electrostatic interactions, and solvent accessibility. These parameters are compared to those in experimentally determined RNA structures. The quantification process involves calculating the likelihood that these features appear in biologically active RNA based on known structures, often utilizing the Boltzmann distribution to relate the energy associated with specific structural features to their probability of occurrence. The earliest methods developed for this purpose were the KB potential⁶¹ and RASP⁶², and later 3dRNAscore⁶³ and DFIRE-RNA⁶⁴. Most recently, rsRNASP⁶⁵ and cgRNASP⁶⁶ were developed based on statistical potentials that consider residue separation along the sequence for RNA 3D structure evaluation to assess the energetic contributions from interactions within RNA 3D structures. While rsRNASP adopts an all-atom framework, cgRNASP employs a coarse-grained approach and additionally models short-ranged interactions by specifically incorporating nearest and next-nearest neighbor residues, providing a more nuanced assessment of local structural features.

DL-based RNA tertiary structure assessment tools employ various methods to score 3D models. Atomic Rotationally Equivariant Scorer (ARES)⁶⁷ is a DL algorithm that predicts the accuracy of RNA 3D structure models in terms of their RMSD to the (unknown) native structure by extracting geometric patterns. It operates without predefined assumptions about structural features essential for accuracy, such

as double helices or canonical or non-canonical base pairs. The network architecture of ARES is specially designed to capture both local and global structural motifs through a process of feature extraction that is sensitive to the geometric arrangement of atoms and their surrounding environment. This design ensures rotational and translational equivariance, allowing ARES to recognize a wide variety of structural motifs, even though the training dataset of known RNA structures was very small. Another method, a feed-forward neural network Root Mean Square Deviation Estimation Algorithm (REA)⁶⁸ also predicts the RMSD of RNA 3D structure models to the native structure, but does it in a very different way. It evaluates the stereochemistry of the 3D model structures by MolProbity⁶⁹, and then utilizes these features for the RMSD prediction. This approach is appropriate for the assessment of models generated by automated 3D structure prediction methods that typically aim at predicting the global 3D structure correctly, without a special focus on local geometry. One weakness of this approach is that it is possible to construct a completely wrong model of RNA 3D structure with perfect stereochemistry that could deceive MolProbity assessment.

RNA3DCNN⁷⁰ is based on the convolutional neural network (CNN) approach. It transforms the 3D atomic model into an array of 3D voxels, capturing nucleotides and their local environments. These voxels are then inputted into a 3D convolutional neural network, which predicts the nucleotide's unfitness score based on RMSD. The method comes in two variants: RNA3DCNN_MD is suitable for assessing near-native structures, whereas RNA3DCNN_MDMC is better suited for evaluating structures covering a wide conformational space. lociPARSE⁷¹ uses a locality-aware invariant point attention model to predict the superimposition-free local distance-difference test (IDDT) scores instead of estimating the RMSD. These scores capture the accuracy of each nucleotide and its surrounding local atomic environment, providing a cumulative assessment of overall global accuracy of a model. RNAGCN⁷² uses a graph convolutional network (GCN) architecture to extract features from the 3D structural information of RNA molecules, represented as graphs, where nodes represent atoms and edges represent chemical bonds or spatial proximities between atoms. It implements multiple GCN layers to employ the information from neighboring nodes in the graph, allowing the model to learn higher-order features that capture the context and interactions between different parts of the RNA structure.

RNAAdvisor⁷³ is a meta-prediction approach for RNA 3D structure assessment. As an input, it takes the results of a number of individual methods such as RASP⁶², rsRNASP⁶⁵, DFIRE-RNA⁶⁴, and ϵ Score⁷⁴, and evaluates critical metrics, including ϵ RMSD, clash RMSD, INF, and p-value.

4. RNA 3D structure modeling informed by experimental data

Methods for RNA 3D structure prediction that have been most successful so far, according to RNA-Puzzles and CASP, particularly those relying on molecular simulations, are well-equipped to incorporate experimental data. This capability allows for a tailored approach to each prediction, adapting to various types of experimental input and enabling researchers to customize their predictions based on specific case requirements. This adaptability ensures that the unique characteristics and constraints of each RNA molecule are considered, resulting in more accurate models. In contrast, current deep learning methods typically rely on standardized input data, usually limited to primary RNA sequences, and are not yet capable of integrating case-dependent experimental data. This reliance on uniform input data is a significant limitation. Overcoming this limitation by enabling deep learning models to incorporate experimental data is one of the promising areas for future improvement (Figure 2).

Figure 2: A comparative overview of data driven modeling approaches for RNA 3D structure prediction. Classical simulation-based methods rely on our understanding of physics and chemistry, and they can incorporate various types of experimental data to tailor predictions for specific cases. Deep learning methods can go beyond our current understanding of physics and chemistry, as long as the relevant information is present and properly represented in the data. Physics- and chemistry-based simulation methods offer detailed insights into RNA folding pathways and conformational transitions and facilitate integrating case-dependent experimental data. Integrating the best features of physics- and chemistry-based approaches suggests areas for potential rapid improvements in deep learning methods.

4.1. RNA 3D structure modeling with the use of chemical probing data

Biochemical RNA structure probing methods provide valuable information about the structural features and dynamics of RNA molecules, ranging from local structural details to global conformational changes^{8,75}. These are broadly categorized into enzymatic probing, chemical probing, and high-throughput probing methods⁷. The general principle underlying these methods is the use of chemical probes to modify RNA at specific functional groups. The modified sites are detected using either reverse transcription with stop (RT-stop) or mutation (RT-mutate) methods. RT-stop methods result in a pool of DNA truncations of different lengths due to the reverse transcription interruption by the adducts, whose frequencies reflect the RNA structure profile, while RT-mutate results in a pool of cDNAs of different sequences by introducing a mismatched nucleotide at the position of the adduct during reverse transcription, which needs to be profiled by high-throughput sequencing (HTS). Further descriptions of the chemical probing methods and advancements were reviewed in these articles⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷. In this review, we mainly focused on the chemical probing that infers tertiary structure information and conformational heterogeneity.

With the use of bifunctional acylation probes, which capture two 2'-hydroxyl residues that are in close spatial proximity, chemical probing methods have become capable of acquiring through-space information in RNA structure⁷⁸. MOHCA is the first such method that can map the positions of nucleotides that are close together in the 3D structure⁷⁹. MOHCA-seq⁸⁰ is an extension of the MOHCA protocol, with mutate-and-map secondary structure inference guiding Rosetta 3D modeling. Recently developed methods that also use bifunctional molecules are SHAPE-JuMP⁸¹ and SHARC⁸².

SHAPE-JuMP⁸¹ combines structure probing with *trans*-bis-isatoic anhydride (TBIA) with proximity ligation to directly map higher-order RNA interactions and tertiary structures. It uses an engineered RT enzyme that 'jumps' across cross-linked sites, resulting in a deletion in the cDNA that is detected using HTS. SHARC⁸² integrates crosslinking, exonuclease (exo) trimming, proximity ligation, and high-throughput sequencing. It has been shown to improve RNA 3D structure modeling to near-nanometer resolution and is the first approach that merges 2'-hydroxyl acylation and computational predictions to directly capture tertiary contacts and alternative conformations of RNAs in their native cellular context. Structural information obtained by SHARC and SHAPE-JuMP methods is limited by the distance between the two acylation-reactive functional groups.

Techniques like RING-MaP (RNA Interaction Groups by Mutational Profiling)⁸³, PAIR-MaP (Parallel Analysis of RNA Interaction by Mutational Profiling)⁸⁴, smCCP (single-molecule Correlated Chemical Probing)⁸⁵ have further advanced the detection of RNA pairing patterns and structural dynamics within living cells, towards the elucidation of RNA secondary and higher-order structures, conformational ensembles, RNA-protein interactions, and allosteric switches.

Structural information obtained from chemical probing data can be incorporated at the stage of secondary structure prediction (which is out of scope for the current review) and to bias the 3D structure prediction. Most conventional methods for RNA 3D structure prediction simulate RNA sequence folding and 3D structure formation, supporting the use of chemical probing data as constraints (e.g., to enforce a specific base-pairing pattern) or restraints (e.g., to improve the scoring of base-pairing patterns that match the reference dataset). Typically, these methods do not accept reactivities, but only interpreted data in the form of specific pairs or spatial distances, and they allow only one specific structure pattern per simulation. Thus, to sample alternative structures, separate calculations with different predefined structural patterns

are usually required. To address this problem, we have recently updated our SimRNA method to enable reading patterns of chemical probing in the form of relative reactivities as an optional input. Additionally, we can define alternative pairing patterns to be considered simultaneously during the 3D structure prediction. We have demonstrated that this approach improves the accuracy of 3D structure prediction for RNAs that assume a single structure or switch between alternative conformations²⁷.

4.2. RNA 3D structure modeling with the use of cryo-EM data

Cryo-electron microscopy with single-particle analysis (cryo-EM SPA) has emerged as a powerful technique for elucidating the 3D structures of macromolecules and their complexes⁸⁶⁻⁸⁸. The method involves suspension of macromolecules in amorphous (vitreous) ice through rapid plunge freezing, which preserve the samples in different orientations of the molecules. By capturing two-dimensional (2D) projections of the particles from diverse orientations, cryo-EM SPA generates a wealth of data that is subsequently used to reconstruct highly detailed 3D structures. However, cryo-EM SPA has largely been limited in its application to RNA-only structures⁸⁸. This can be attributed to two key challenges: I. Size limitations: Many RNA targets of interest are smaller than 50 kDa, making them difficult to resolve using cryo-EM SPA. This limitation can be addressed by the RNA scaffolding approach, which involves the fusion of the RNA of interest with a larger, well-structured RNA of known 3D structure^{89,90}. II. Conformational dynamics: Many RNAs are inherently flexible, which hinders the collection of a large number of single-particle images for one specific conformation that is necessary for the determination of that conformation's 3D structure. As a result, many cryo-EM experiments for RNA yield 3D structure models of relatively low resolution. This limitation has been addressed by hybrid approaches that involve computational modeling.

DRRAFTER⁹¹ was a pioneering method for computational modeling of RNA 3D structures into cryo-EM maps that required user-placed initial helical fragments of RNA for protein-RNA complex modeling. Auto-DRRAFTER⁹² is a next generation software that automates many steps of the DRRAFTER method. However, it has various restrictions, particularly it requires defined secondary structure information. It has been integrated into the Ribosolve pipeline⁹³, which is an overall methodological workflow for RNA structure modeling based on cryo-EM data. It combines cryo-EM single-particle analysis, M2-seq biochemical analysis, and 3D modeling with restraints to accelerate 3D RNA structure determination. Using this approach, 3D models have been generated for diverse RNA molecules at resolutions ranging from 4.7 to 10 Å.

CryoREAD⁹⁴ represents a pioneering DL method for fully automated de novo modeling of DNA/RNA structures into cryo-EM maps. It predicts potential locations of phosphates, sugars, and nucleobases based on characteristic local density patterns. Subsequently, the identified sugar positions are linked to generate the backbone structure. CryoREAD works well for nucleic acid structures for maps at high resolution. It can also generate models for maps with lower resolutions (>5 Å), but in such cases, it can err concerning nucleotide sequence assignment. The final model may contain gaps in the backbone and incorrect base-pairing conformations, especially for larger structures at low resolution. DiffModeler⁹⁵ utilizes a diffusion model-based approach for 3D structure modeling from cryo-EM maps. While primarily designed for protein structures, it can also be used for modeling protein-RNA complexes by incorporating RNA models predicted by CryoREAD. This integration offers promise for building more comprehensive models of protein-RNA interactions observed in cryo-EM data. EMRNA⁹⁶ takes a multi-pronged approach, combining DL-based nucleotide detection with 3D backbone tracing and scoring sequence and secondary

structure information for full-atom RNA structure construction. It employs DL to predict the RNA main-chain. Subsequently, the predicted main-chain information is utilized to build complete RNA structures by integrating the traced 3D backbones with the 1D sequence and predicted 2D secondary structure. Challenges remain, particularly regarding accurately tracing long RNA molecules and structure determination for maps at resolution worse than 4 Å.

DoubleHelix⁹⁷ is a program developed for the identification and validation of nucleic acid sequences in cryo-EM maps, as well as electron density maps obtained by X-ray crystallography. As an input it requires a backbone model of the RNA structure, and a density map. It combines a neural network classifier of nucleobase identities and a sequence-independent secondary structure assignment. It works effectively with local resolutions up to 5 Å.

4.3. RNA 3D Structure modeling with the use of low-resolution small angle X-ray scattering data

Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) provides valuable information in solution and can be particularly useful when high-resolution structures are unavailable. SAXS measures the intensity of X-rays scattered by a molecule at low angles, providing information about its overall shape and dimensions in its native state, leading to a more accurate representation of the RNA structure in solution. By collecting SAXS data under different conditions (e.g., varying temperature or presence of ligands), insights can be gained into how RNA molecules change their shape in response to their environment⁹⁸.

The development of computational tools for the analysis of SAXS data has aided in the study of RNA 3D structures in solution. Among the early contributions to this field, the ATSAS package^{99,100} was developed as a comprehensive suite designed for the processing, analysis, and modeling of SAXS data for any type of biomacromolecules, including proteins and nucleic acids. Within the ATSAS suite, DAMMIN¹⁰¹ and GASBOR¹⁰² are tools for generating coarse-grained models that align with experimental SAXS profiles. These 3D models depict the general shapes of RNA structures without assigning specific atoms to precise spatial positions. For the task of evaluating 3D structure models against SAXS data, applicable to protein as well as RNA structures, several tools were developed, including CRY SOL¹⁰³, FoXS¹⁰⁴, SASStbx¹⁰⁵ and Pepsi-SAXS¹⁰⁶. These methods were designed to compute scattering profiles from atomic models, allowing for a direct comparison with experimental SAXS data. They each have unique features, providing a range of options. For instance, Pepsi-SAXS is recognized for its speed in calculating scattering profiles. However, these methods have limitations, particularly they require pre-existing 3D structure models to compute scattering profiles. This necessitates complementary techniques to generate the 3D models for the subsequent scoring. One of the first approaches was the Fast-SAXS-RNA approach, which involved the generation of RNA 3D structure models with the MC-Fold and MC-Sym pipeline¹⁰⁷ followed by the assessment of these models by the SAXS data¹⁰⁸.

More recently, methods were developed that take the SAXS data into account directly into the modeling process. RNA Masonry¹⁰⁹ is a method that assembles RNA 3D structure models from fragments obtained from the RNA Bricks database¹¹⁰, which are scored by the SimRNA potential²⁶. The model building can be restrained with a goodness-of-fit to the experimental small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) data, calculated using FoXS or CRY SOL. Several approaches have also been developed to combine SAXS data with MD simulations. One recent example is the hySAS (hybrid-resolution small-angle scattering) method¹¹¹, which is applicable for both protein and RNA molecules, implements a coarse-grained representation consisting of one bead per amino acid and three beads per nucleic acid, and accounts for

solvation effects. This model is coupled with MD simulations restrained with SAS data, to determine conformational ensembles or refine the structure and dynamics of macromolecules. Another approach is sampling the RNA 3D structures using the ERNWIN method and evaluating them with the SPQR scoring function and experimental SAXS data¹¹².

4.4. RNA 3D Structure modeling with the use of very low-resolution approaches

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) is widely used in the analysis of nucleic acids, including RNA. This technique provides information on the structural details of individual molecules by measuring the force between a sharp probe and the sample surface. It is particularly useful for visualizing the topography and mechanical properties of nucleic acids without the need for labels. It allows the imaging of RNAs of essentially unlimited size¹¹³. The ability of AFM to operate in both air and liquid environments makes it very versatile. In particular, conducting AFM in solution maintains the RNA in a state close to its natural aqueous environment, thereby preserving its conformation and biological activity. It is well-suited for studying highly heterogeneous molecular systems, such as RNA molecules characterized by high conformational variability. It has been successfully applied to visualize the structure and motion of RNAs as small as the adenosyl cobalamin riboswitch aptamer domain¹¹⁴ and as large as the lncRNA HOTAIR¹¹⁵. HORNET¹¹⁶ is a recently developed computational method for determining RNA 3D structures from AFM images of individual RNA molecules in solution, using unsupervised machine learning, and deep neural networks. This approach is particularly suited for capturing the structures of conformationally heterogeneous RNA molecules in solution, addressing a significant challenge in RNA structural biology.

Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) allows for studying highly dynamic systems and is providing valuable insights into the behavior and folding patterns of RNA molecules¹¹⁷. The method exploits the transfer of energy between two fluorophores (donor and acceptor) when they are in close proximity, and it is used to monitor the distances between labeled positions. While the method doesn't provide high resolution information, it can be applied to RNA molecules at a single-molecule level and close to physiological conditions. It has been used e.g., to analyze the structure of the hammerhead ribozyme, when neither crystal nor a solution structure were available¹¹⁸, to analyze the twister ribozyme folding in response to different metal ions¹¹⁹, and to study ligand-dependent co-transcriptional folding of the *E. coli* thiM riboswitch¹²⁰. Recently, a computational framework has been proposed to use single-molecule FRET measurements with MD simulations and de novo structure prediction with Rosetta. FRET data has been incorporated as a post-hoc scoring method¹²¹.

5. Remaining challenges, the future of RNA 3D structure prediction, and its potential impact on our understanding of RNA biology:

Accurately predicting 3D structures of RNA molecules remains a significant challenge. This complexity arises from several key factors. Firstly, unlike proteins that often adopt a single stable conformation, RNA exhibits inherent structural heterogeneity. This characteristic allows RNA to exist in many stable and transient conformations, each potentially associated with distinct functional states. Current computational tools struggle to capture this dynamic nature, hindering the accurate prediction of RNA structures. Secondly, the effectiveness of predictive models, particularly those employing DL techniques, is heavily constrained by the availability of high-resolution RNA structure data. Existing datasets are often

insufficient to train sophisticated models, which require extensive and high-quality input data for accurate predictions. This limitation is further exacerbated by the inherent challenges associated with experimentally determining detailed RNA structures, often resulting from conformational flexibility and variability.

To overcome these obstacles, the field of RNA 3D structure determination requires computational methods capable of accurately reflecting the dynamic nature of RNA and predicting a broader spectrum of RNA conformations, rather than just generating one 3D structure model for a particular RNA sequence. A key may be the incorporation of additional experimental data. Many research groups have already attempted to integrate data from variable sources, including information from the local structural state of individual residues or the spatial proximity of residues (e.g., from chemical probing and FRET analyses) to the global shapes of molecules (e.g., from cryo-EM, SAXS, and AFM). Currently, the most promising method seems to be the cryo-EM. While advancements in cryo-EM have improved the speed at which RNA 3D structures are determined (review⁸⁸), interpreting structures at lower resolutions remains a significant hurdle. The successful implementation of computational methods for RNA 3D structure prediction hinges on the development of comprehensive and high-quality training datasets, which are currently lacking for RNA structures.

As the field of RNA 3D structure prediction continues to evolve, its potential to revolutionize our understanding of RNA biology and significantly impact the field of molecular medicine becomes increasingly evident. The integration of advanced computational models with diverse experimental data holds promise for enhancing the accuracy and reliability of RNA 3D structure predictions. This advancement is a stepping stone towards identifying novel RNA targets for therapeutic interventions, particularly in complex diseases where RNA plays a central role in regulation.

With improved accuracy in predicting RNA 3D structure and its dynamics, the applications of computational predictive methods in drug discovery are poised to expand. The ability to precisely predict RNA 3D structures and their conformational variability will facilitate the design of small molecules and other therapeutic agents that can specifically target RNA molecules involved in disease processes. This targeted approach may be particularly valuable in conditions such as cancer and viral infections, where RNA structures are intricately linked to the molecular pathology of the disease¹²².

Recently, a number of new methods were developed to predict RNA 3D structures in complexes with small molecules. One type of method uses scoring functions for the assessment of RNA-ligand complexes obtained by docking methods such as AnnapuRNA¹²³ or RmsdXNA¹²⁴. Recently, our group employed Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to develop a method to predict ligand binding activity toward RNA targets¹²⁵. Prototypes of methods to predict 3D structures of RNA-small molecule complexes have also been developed, including SimRNA-ligand (our unpublished data), and AlphaFold3⁴¹, but they remain to be tested in rigorous benchmarks.

The growing success of RNA-targeted therapies, such as antisense oligonucleotides and RNA-based vaccines, underscores the critical role of understanding RNA structures^{126,127}. These therapeutic approaches rely on the precise targeting of RNA functional states, which can be significantly enhanced by detailed structural insights. The success of mRNA-based vaccines during the COVID-19 pandemic exemplifies the potential of RNA-targeted approaches in rapid vaccine development¹²⁸.

In conclusion, the advancement of RNA 3D structure prediction technology has deepened our understanding of RNA biology, and continues to pave the way for the development of novel therapeutic strategies that exploit the intricate details of RNA function. This progression is likely to lead to the development of more effective and targeted treatments for a wide range of diseases, marking a significant milestone in the evolution of personalized medicine.

Disclaimer

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT, Gemini, and Grammarly in order to proof-read the text to enhance the quality of the language. After using these software tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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